

An Evaluation of Existing Measures and Interventions for Addressing Substance Abuse in the Public Sector: Evidence from Morogoro Municipality, Tanzania

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Abstract

This study evaluated existing measures and interventions addressing substance abuse in the public sector, with specific reference to Morogoro Municipality, Tanzania. Guided by Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, the research examined how personal, environmental, and behavioural factors influence substance use among employees. A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews. A sample of 100 participants was drawn from a population of 4,798 public servants across multiple departments, using stratified random and purposive sampling techniques. Data were analysed through descriptive statistics, SPSS-based inferential analysis, and thematic analysis. Findings revealed that substance abuse is a visible and growing concern, with alcohol and marijuana being the most commonly abused substances. Substance abuse negatively impacted employee performance, contributing to absenteeism, lateness, misconduct, and productivity decline. Interventions reported were largely disciplinary in nature warnings, transfers, suspensions, or dismissals with limited rehabilitative or preventive programs. Awareness of interventions was low, and employees expressed demand for structured policies, confidential counselling, and workplace education. The study concludes that interventions in Morogoro Municipality are inadequate, reactive, and inconsistent. It recommends the development of comprehensive workplace policies, confidential support systems, budgetary allocations, and integration of government-led strategies.

Keywords: *Substance abuse, Workplace interventions, Public sector, Employee performance.*

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Introduction

Substance abuse in the workplace is a growing concern worldwide, threatening both individual wellbeing and organizational efficiency.

Globally, it is estimated that substance use contributes to billions of dollars in lost productivity annually, alongside increased absenteeism, workplace accidents, and declining employee morale (WHO, 2023). In many low-

and middle-income countries, including Tanzania, the situation is compounded by limited resources for prevention and treatment, weak workplace policies, and inadequate integration of mental health services into employment systems. This creates a dual challenge: while the prevalence of substance use is increasing, institutional responses remain inadequate.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, public institutions are particularly affected due to systemic weaknesses in policy implementation and limited access to rehabilitation services. Studies in Kenya and South Africa have shown that even where workplace policies exist, they are often poorly enforced, with punitive measures taking precedence over preventive or rehabilitative approaches (Kamenderi et al., 2022; Smook et al., 2018). Tanzania has similarly witnessed a rising trend in alcohol and cannabis consumption among working populations, with prescription drug misuse emerging as a new concern (DCEA, 2023). In public institutions, stressors such as limited resources, high workloads, and poor remuneration contribute to vulnerability, yet very few interventions adequately address the root causes of substance abuse.

Morogoro Municipality provides a critical case study for examining workplace substance use in Tanzania. As a fast-growing urban center with a workforce of over 4,000 public servants, it reflects both the pressures of urbanization and the challenges of service delivery in education, health, and administrative sectors. Reports from the Drug Control and Enforcement Authority (2022) identify Morogoro as one of the municipalities experiencing an alarming rise in substance abuse, particularly alcohol, marijuana, and misuse of prescription drugs. Given the central role of public servants in delivering essential services, substance use within this sector threatens not only institutional performance but also community welfare.

Theoretically, this study draws on Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986), which emphasizes the interaction between individual behaviors, social environments, and organizational cultures. The theory provides a

useful lens for understanding how workplace environments either discourage or perpetuate substance use, depending on the presence of supportive interventions. Against this background, the study aims to examine the prevalence of substance abuse among public sector employees in Morogoro Municipality, assess its effects on job performance, and evaluate the effectiveness of existing interventions. The study also seeks to provide evidence-based recommendations for strengthening workplace responses to substance abuse in Tanzania.

Materials and Methods

This study adopted a mixed-methods design, integrating both quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a comprehensive understanding of substance abuse in the public sector. It was conducted in Morogoro Municipality, located 190 kilometers west of Dar es Salaam, with a total workforce of 4,798 public servants across multiple departments. A sample size of 100 respondents was determined using Yamane's (1967) formula, and participants were selected through stratified random sampling to ensure representation of key divisions such as education, health, and administration, while purposive sampling identified key informants including departmental heads and human resource officers. Data were collected through structured questionnaires to capture prevalence, substance types, and effects on performance, alongside semi-structured interviews to explore institutional responses and gaps. Ethical clearance was obtained from the University of Iringa Research Ethics Committee and permissions were secured from municipal authorities, with informed consent and confidentiality assured for all participants. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS, which provided descriptive and inferential statistics, while qualitative data were transcribed and analyzed thematically to identify recurring patterns and narratives. Methodological triangulation of quantitative and qualitative findings strengthened validity and reliability, ensuring the results captured both statistical trends and lived experiences.

Results

Existing Measures and Interventions Addressing Substance Abuse in the Public Sector

Substance abuse within the public sector is not only a behavioral and health issue but a systemic challenge that demands structured institutional responses. Given its adverse impact on productivity, service delivery, and employee wellbeing, effective intervention frameworks are crucial. This section discusses existing intervention strategies as reported in the current study and compares them with best practices and findings from recent literature (2018–2024). Data from both the quantitative survey and qualitative interviews reveal gaps between recognition of the problem and the structured response. While some employees report the presence of policies and disciplinary measures, there is clear inconsistency in implementation, awareness, and support-based strategies such as counseling or rehabilitation.

Awareness and Availability of Interventions

Quantitative data reveals that only 54% of the respondent's reported knowledge of any substance abuse intervention programs at their workplace. The remaining 46% either denied the existence of such programs (25%) or were unaware (21%). This suggests a lack of institutional visibility or communication around available interventions. The interviews further support this claim; several interviewees stated they had no knowledge of active policies or support systems, which is concerning given the documented prevalence of substance use among public sector employees in this municipality.

These findings resonate with the work of Kainika (2019) and Kamenderi et al. (2022), who highlight how a lack of institutional clarity and communication often prevents civil servants from accessing substance abuse interventions. Similarly, the ILO (2023) stresses that for any workplace policy to be effective, its visibility and perceived legitimacy must be high among employees.

Types of Measures Used

The responses gathered during interviews show that most measures reported by participants are disciplinary in nature. These include verbal warnings, suspensions, and in severe cases, termination. For instance, one interviewee noted that “if a person is found using drugs, the organization might decide to transfer them to another station or issue a warning.” In other cases, employees are “dismissed after repeated infractions.”

While these approaches aim to preserve organizational order, they fall short of addressing the root causes of substance abuse. Studies such as Morse et al. (2022) and Akanbi et al. (2020) caution against relying solely on punitive methods, noting that without psychological support or medical treatment, affected employees are unlikely to rehabilitate. In fact, the Drug Control and Enforcement Authority (DCEA, 2023) and the WHO (2021) recommend a balance between disciplinary enforcement and rehabilitation, advocating for the establishment of Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs) that offer counseling and addiction management services.

Despite the prevalence of punitive measures, there is emerging evidence of support-based strategies within some departments. Interviewees mentioned occasional seminars on workplace ethics and the involvement of mental health professionals in counselling. For example, Interview 8 notes that “there are programs involving mental health professionals who provide education and counselling.” Interview 4 highlights routine education every Monday about expected behaviour, which may function as a preventive measure.

Although limited in scope, such strategies represent steps toward a more humane and effective response. These align with the WHO's (2023) emphasis on early intervention, psychosocial counselling, and harm reduction as key elements of workplace substance use mitigation. Furthermore, Grant (2022) and Sorge et al. (2020) argue that employee-focused interventions (e.g., access to therapists, flexible rehabilitation leave, and peer mentoring) reduce

not only drug dependency but also absenteeism, thus contributing to long-term productivity.

The findings of this study revealed that institutional responses to substance abuse in Morogoro Municipality remain inadequate, largely reactive, and heavily disciplinary. With nearly half of employees either unaware of interventions or reporting their absence, and many describing existing measures as “warnings,” “transfers,” or “dismissals,” the study portrays a system ill-prepared to address the root causes of substance abuse. Yet, contrasting perspectives in the wider literature suggest that the situation may not always be as limited as it appears, and that even punitive or ad hoc strategies can sometimes provide short-term relief.

For example, Agboh (2016), in his study of Ghanaian police officers, noted that while punitive measures such as transfers and suspensions are often criticized as unsustainable, they did manage to temporarily deter visible substance abuse within the force. This contrasts with the consensus from Morogoro respondents who emphasized the ineffectiveness of such measures. It suggests that disciplinary actions, though limited, may serve as an immediate control strategy in some contexts, particularly where rehabilitation resources are scarce.

Similarly, Kamenderi et al. (2022) found that in Kenya, awareness programs, workplace meetings, and periodic ethics training contributed to maintaining a moderate level of control over substance use in the public sector. While employees often underestimated these programs’ effectiveness, supervisors reported that they helped reduce overt workplace intoxication. This contrasts with the Morogoro case where education and awareness efforts were rarely formalized and employees expressed near-universal demand for policy-driven solutions.

Effectiveness of Measures

When asked about the effectiveness of interventions, 32% of participants rated them as “effective,” and 17% as “very effective.” However, a significant portion, 33%, reported being “not sure,” and another 17% indicated that no interventions exist. This spread indicates

that while some programs might be working effectively, there is inconsistency in either reach or implementation.

This mirrors findings from Lelei et al. (2022), who studied the Kenyan public sector and found that even where policies existed, poor institutional commitment and lack of trained personnel led to ineffective application. Likewise, Smook et al. (2018) argue that fragmented application of workplace drug policies reduces their credibility among employees and undermines their long-term efficacy.

Recommendations from Employees

One of the strongest themes to emerge from the interviews was a repeated call for more education and policy improvements. Interviewees proposed measures such as increased funding for awareness campaigns, the inclusion of psychologists, peer-led counseling, and a revision of workplace policy frameworks. Interview 9 emphasized that “strict laws should be implemented,” while Interview 10 argued for “training and more research” to better understand the problem.

The literature supports these proposals. Malick (2018) and the EMCDDA (2023) assert that preventive education and periodic drug-screening programs help reduce workplace drug-related incidents. In addition, Ndumwa et al. (2022) stress the importance of embedding substance use interventions into broader workplace wellness policies, especially in sectors like healthcare and education where the risks are magnified.

Departmental Variation in Intervention Access

Another important pattern was the variation in responses depending on the department. While some interviewees reported well-structured responses, including routine education and mental health access, others (particularly in smaller or decentralized units) reported no knowledge or access to intervention measures. Interview 2, for example, stated plainly, “In my department, there is no one who uses those drugs, so no measures have been taken.”

This variation underscores the need for uniform, centrally enforced policies across departments. Adekanmbi & Ukpere (2020) found that inconsistent application of policies across departments in Nigerian civil service significantly contributed to gaps in intervention effectiveness and employee trust. Similarly, Agboh (2016) observed that within the Ghana Police Service, the absence of universal protocols meant that some officers had better access to support than others, despite being equally at risk.

Policy Integration and Government Involvement

The study participants overwhelmingly supported stronger government involvement in designing and implementing workplace interventions. Several interviewees advocated for centrally coordinated rehabilitation support, policy reform, and increased funding. This call aligns with the recommendations of the Drug Control and Enforcement Authority (DCEA, 2024), which advocates a national framework for workplace drug intervention supported by ministries and public commissions.

According to ILO (2023) policy recommendations, effective responses must integrate national policy, institutional leadership, and employee participation. Furthermore, World Health Organization (2024) highlights the importance of multi-level interventions, combining policy, education, and treatment that respond not only to substance use but also to underlying stressors and work conditions.

Theoretical Interpretation: Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (SCT)

In the language of the Social Cognitive Theory, the employees are demanding a change to the "environment" factor of Bandura's (1986) model. They implicitly recognize that individual behavioral change is incredibly difficult without a supportive, structured environment. Their call for policies, education, and accessible support is a call to build a healthier organizational culture one that prevents substance abuse, destigmatizes seeking help, and offers pathways to recovery rather.

Implication and Reflection

This goal showed a worrying disparity between the rates of substance abuse and the effectiveness of institutional reactions. Although some workers indicated that they were aware of interventions, almost half said they did not know of any programs, and many considered current reactions as reactive and punitive. This indicates that the interventions are either underpublicized or inefficient and proves previous criticisms of Morse et al. (2022) and Akanbi et al. (2020) that disciplinary actions alone cannot serve as a solution to underlying causes. The statistics suggest that it is high time to switch to holistic and preventive approaches to disciplinary models that encompass education, confidential counselling, as well as employee involvement. Also, the unanimity in the desire to have better workplace policies attests to the high level of willingness to change institutions. Policy-wise, this fact highlights the significance of adopting the Occupational Health and Safety Act (2003) and the Public Service Management and Employment Policy (2020) on the local level more efficiently. Finally, it is crucial to develop a stigma-free and positive workplace environment to support both the health and the productivity of the organization.

Conclusion

The study concludes that substance abuse is a visible and persistent problem in the public sector of Morogoro Municipality, with alcohol and marijuana being the most frequently reported substances. The prevalence of substance use is strongly linked to stressful work environments, limited coping mechanisms, and weak institutional policies. Its effects on employee performance are severe, including absenteeism, lateness, low productivity, and disciplinary issues, all of which compromise service delivery in vital sectors such as health and education.

The interventions currently in place were found to be largely inadequate, characterized mainly by punitive responses such as warnings, transfers, or dismissals. These measures do not address the underlying causes of substance use and may even exacerbate the problem by driving affected employees into silence or denial. Preventive and

rehabilitative strategies, such as awareness campaigns, counselling, and structured policies, were either absent or poorly implemented. This indicates a significant gap between recognition of the problem and the institutional response.

Overall, the findings underscore the urgent need for a paradigm shift in how substance abuse is addressed in Tanzania's public sector. Rather than relying on reactive disciplinary actions, institutions must adopt holistic and preventive frameworks that combine education, counselling, and rehabilitation with fair enforcement of workplace policies. Such an approach would not only protect employee wellbeing but also strengthen institutional performance and service delivery in the long run.

Recommendations

To address the challenges identified, this study recommends several policy and institutional measures. First, there is an urgent need to develop and institutionalize workplace substance abuse policies across all public institutions. These policies should not only prohibit substance use but also define clear procedures for early detection, intervention, and rehabilitation. Embedding such frameworks into human resource manuals and codes of conduct would ensure consistency and legitimacy in their application.

Second, institutions should establish confidential support and rehabilitation mechanisms, such as Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs). These programs would provide counselling, psychological support, and referrals to rehabilitation services, enabling employees to seek help without fear of job loss or stigma. Confidentiality and accessibility are critical in fostering trust and encouraging employees to utilize such services.

Third, the government and local authorities should allocate adequate budgetary resources to support intervention programs. Without sustainable funding, even well-designed policies and programs risk failing in implementation. Investment should cover staff training, awareness campaigns, rehabilitation support, and collaboration with mental health professionals.

Fourth, there is a need for awareness and education campaigns to address stigma and misconceptions surrounding substance abuse. These campaigns should involve all stakeholders, including employees, supervisors, and community leaders, and should emphasize that substance use is a health issue requiring supportive responses rather than moral condemnation.

Finally, interventions must be integrated and applied uniformly across departments to eliminate disparities in access and effectiveness. A centrally coordinated approach led by government agencies, in collaboration with institutions, would ensure fairness and build employee trust in workplace interventions. Through these measures, substance abuse can be addressed not only as a disciplinary concern but as a systemic issue requiring preventive, rehabilitative, and supportive action.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Adekanmbi, F. P., & Ukpere, W. I. (2020). Individual substance abuse, perceived workplace fairness and organisational factors as predictors of absenteeism among civil servants in Oyo State. *Journal of Psychology and Education*, 57, 309–323.
- Agboh, H. N. K. (2016). *Alcohol-use at the workplace: The case of police divisions operating under the Accra Regional Command of the Ghana Police Service* (Doctoral dissertation). University of Ghana.
- Akanbi, M. O., Iroz, C. B., O'Dwyer, L. C., Rivera, A. S., & McHugh, M. C. (2020). A systematic review of the effectiveness of employer-led interventions for drug misuse.

Journal of Occupational Health, 62(1), e12133.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/13489585.12133>

Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Prentice-Hall.

Drug Control and Enforcement Authority (DCEA). (2022). *Annual report on substance abuse in Tanzania*.

Drug Control and Enforcement Authority (DCEA). (2023). *Annual report on drug abuse in Tanzania*.

Drug Control and Enforcement Authority (DCEA). (2024, May). *Drug status report 2023*.
<https://www.dcea.go.tz/publications/drug-situation-report>

European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction (EMCDDA). (2023). *Trends in workplace drug use in Europe*.
https://www.euda.europa.eu/publications/european-drug-report/2023_en

Grant, V. A. (2022). *Effective strategies to prevent and reduce substance abuse in the workplace* (Doctoral dissertation). Walden University.

International Labour Organization (ILO). (2023). *Workplace safety and substance abuse policy recommendations*.
https://www.ilo.org/global/publications/WCMS_909180/lang-en/index.htm

Kainika, O. T. N. (2019). *The effects of drug and substance abuse on employees' job performance on selected insurance companies in Nairobi, Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation). United States International University–Africa.

Kamenderi, M. K. M., Muteti, J. M. J., Kimani, S. K. S., & Okioma, V. O. V. (2022). Alcohol use disorders and associated determinants among public sector employees in Kenya. *African Journal of Alcohol and Drug Abuse*, 7(2), 3–10.

Lelei, K., Muteti, J., Njenga, A., & Okioma, V. (2022). Policy brief on the status of alcohol and drug abuse among employees in the public sector workplace in Kenya. *African Journal of Alcohol and Drug Abuse*, 7(2).

Malick, R. (2018). Prevention of substance use disorders in the community and workplace.

Indian Journal of Psychiatry, 60(Suppl. 4), S559–S563.

https://doi.org/10.4103/psychiatry.IndianJPsychiatry_24_18

Morse, A. K., Askovic, M., Sercombe, J., Dean, K., Fisher, A., Marel, C., Chatterton, M.-L., Kay-Lambkin, F., Barrett, E., Sunderland, M., Harvey, L., Peach, N., Teesson, M., & Mills, K. L. (2022). A systematic review of the efficacy, effectiveness, and cost-effectiveness of workplace-based interventions for the prevention and treatment of problematic substance use. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 1051119.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.1051119>

Ndumwa, H. P., Munishi, C., Ngowi, J. E., Njiro, B. J., Mabusu, M., Suhartono, S., Busse, A., Campello, G., Garofalo, G., Cipolla, P., Nyandindi, C., Ubuguyu, O., & Sunguya, B. (2022). Drug use and associated factors in a northeastern region of Tanzania: A cross-sectional study. *Pan African Medical Journal*, 43, 70.
<https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2022.43.70.35059>

Smook, B., Ubbink, M., Ryke, E., & Strydom, H. (2018). Substance abuse and the workplace: A situation analysis. *Social Work*, 54(2), 194–209.

Sorge, J. T., Young, M., Maloney-Hall, B., Sherk, A., Kent, P., Zhao, J., ... & Ferguson, B. (2020). Estimation of the impacts of substance use on workplace productivity: A hybrid human capital and prevalence-based approach applied to Canada. *Canadian Journal of Public Health*, 111(2), 202–211. <https://doi.org/10.17269/s41997-019-00272-5>

World Health Organization. (2021). *Global report on substance use disorders*.

World Health Organization. (2023). *Global status report on substance abuse 2023*.

World Health Organization. (2024). *Substance abuse*. WHO Regional Office for Africa.
<https://www.afro.who.int/health-topics/substance-abuse>